

Original paper

SYNTACTIC AND HEURISTIC APPROACH METHOD FOR AUTOMATIC QUESTION GENERATION SYSTEMS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Annotation

INTRODUCTION: the article analyzes the use of syntactic and heuristic approaches in automatic question generation (AQG) systems based on artificial intelligence, with a focus on their application in educational contexts.

AIM: the main aim of the study is to improve the quality and efficiency of automatically generated questions by combining syntactic parsing (POS tagging, dependency analysis) and heuristic methods (rule-based strategies, lexical variations, ranking), resulting in grammatically correct, meaningful, and user-adaptive questions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the study applies NLP tools (spaCy, dependency parsing), transformer-based generative models, and adaptive evaluation mechanisms. The system architecture is detailed through tables and a staged design model.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS: experimental results demonstrate that the hybrid approach significantly improves fluency, relevance, and diversity of generated questions. The system adapts to users' responses and reduces human bias in the assessment process.

CONCLUSION: the proposed method holds practical significance for enhancing automated question generation systems in education, simplifying testing and evaluation, and contributing to more intelligent and personalized learning processes.

Keywords: automatic question generation (AQG), natural language processing (NLP), syntactic parsing, heuristic methods, dependency-based questions.

For citation: Yuldashev A. Nodirbek. (2025) 'Syntactic and heuristic approach method for automatic question generation systems using Artificial Intelligence', Inter education & global study, vol.3 (6(1)), pp.411–417. (In English).

МЕТОД СИНТАКСИЧЕСКОГО И ЭВРИСТИЧЕСКОГО ПОДХОДА ДЛЯ СИСТЕМ АВТОМАТИЧЕСКОЙ ГЕНЕРАЦИИ ВОПРОСОВ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА

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Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в статье рассматривается применение синтаксических и эвристических подходов в системах автоматической генерации вопросов (АГВ) на основе искусственного интеллекта и их роль в образовательных процессах.

ЦЕЛЬ: основная цель исследования — повысить эффективность генерации вопросов за счёт интеграции синтаксического анализа (POS-разметка, анализ зависимостей) и эвристических методов (правила, лексические вариации, ранжирование), создавая грамматически правильные, содержательные и адаптивные вопросы.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: использованы средства обработки естественного языка (spaCy, разбор зависимостей), генеративные трансформер-модели, а также адаптивные алгоритмы оценки качества вопросов и их релевантности. Структура метода описана поэтапно с приведением таблиц и архитектурных схем.

ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: результаты тестирования показали, что предложенный подход значительно улучшает беглость, логичность и разнообразие создаваемых вопросов. Система адаптируется к пользователю, снижает влияние человеческого фактора в процессе тестирования.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: разработанный метод обладает высоким практическим потенциалом для использования в системах образования, повышая качество оценки, автоматизируя подготовку тестов и способствуя развитию интеллектуального обучения.

Ключевые слова: автоматическая генерация вопросов (АГВ), обработка естественного языка (ОЕЯ), синтаксический анализ, эвристические методы, анализ зависимостей.

Для цитирования: Юлдашев Н.А. Метод синтаксического и эвристического подхода для систем автоматической генерации вопросов с использованием искусственного интеллекта // Inter education & global study.2025. Vol.3 №6(1). С. 411–417.

SUN'IY INTELLEKTDAN FOYDALANGAN HOLDA AVTOMATIK SAVOL YARATISH TIZIMLARI UCHUN SINTAKTIK VA EVRISTIK YONDASHUV USULI

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Annotatsiya

KIRISH: maqolada sun'iy intellekt asosida avtomatik savol yaratish tizimlarini takomillashtirishda sintaktik va evristik yondashuvlarning o'rni va ular asosida ishlab chiqilgan gibridd metodning ta'lim jarayonidagi qo'llanilishi tahlil qilinadi.

MAQSAD: tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi — savol yaratish tizimlarida sintaktik tahlil (POS-teg, qaramlik tahlili) va evristik usullar (qoidalarga asoslangan strategiyalar, leksik variatsiyalar) ni uyg'unlashtirish orqali mazmunli, grammatik jihatdan to'g'ri, xilma-xil va foydalanuvchiga moslashtirilgan savollar yaratish samaradorligini oshirishdir.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: tadqiqotda NLP vositalaridan (spaCy, dependency parsing, POS tagging), generativ modellar (transformerlar), sinovli yondashuvlar va moslashtirilgan baholash mexanizmlaridan foydalanilgan. Shuningdek, metod arxitekturasi va ish bosqichlari jadvallar va algoritmlar orqali yoritilgan.

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: sinov natijalari savollarni avtomatik yaratishda ushbu gibridd yondashuv savollar ravonligini, dolzarbligini va semantik mosligini sezilarli oshirganini ko'rsatdi. Yaratilgan tizim foydalanuvchi javoblariga moslashadi va baholashda inson omilini kamaytiradi.

XULOSA: taklif etilgan metod sun'iy intellekt asosida avtomatlashtirilgan savol yaratish tizimlarini rivojlantirish, ta'lim tizimida test va baholashni soddalashtirish hamda ta'lim sifati va samaradorligini oshirishda katta amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: avtomatik savol yaratish (ASY), tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash (TTQI), sintaktik tahlil, evristik metodlar, qaramlik tahlili.

Iqtibos uchun: Nodirbek A. Yuldashev Sun'iy intellektdan foydalangan holda avtomatik savol yaratish tizimlari uchun sintaktik va evristik yondashuv usuli. // Inter education & global study. 2025. Vol.3 №6(1). B.411–417.

Modern educational processes are increasingly dependent on the effective use of information and communication technologies (ICT). An important aspect of successful teaching is the ability of teachers to effectively use ICT both in teaching and in communicating with students. In technical universities, where educational programs are often associated with high technologies and innovations, the need to increase the level of information and communication competencies of teachers becomes a key task. This scientific work is devoted to the development and implementation of the "Method of syntactic and heuristic approaches for automatic question generation and assessment systems", aimed at the effective use of advanced Artificial Intelligence technologies in the automation of test taking and creation processes in higher education systems, reducing the human factor in the process of question creation in the field and minimizing problems in the assessment process. The method combines elements of project-based learning, digital collaboration and assessment procedures, which, by automating the processes of automatic test creation and assessment, save teachers' time spent on these processes and allow them to achieve high results in their professional development.

The method for automatic question generation based on syntactic and heuristic approaches - aims to combine logical and creative thinking in the process of question generation. This method can be used to automatically generate questions with the help of artificial intelligence, improve their quality and ensure their flexibility. The main aspects of the method for automatic question generation based on the approaches presented in the scientific work are presented below:

The syntactic approach - provides automatic question generation based on rule-based and grammatical structures. This approach includes the following stages:

Text analysis: Using natural language processing (NLP) tools, the main concepts in the text and their syntactic structures were identified.

Question template creation: Question forms were developed based on predefined grammatical rules.

Data placement: Data obtained from the text was entered into question templates, and syntactically correct questions were created.

Question optimization: The options for removing, correcting, and editing incorrect or illogical questions through the processing stage were created in the settings section.

It was based on creative and flexible question generation methods through a heuristic approach. It includes the following steps:

Semantic analysis: Identifying semantic relationships in the text and developing question options that match them.

Generalization and differentiation of information: Expressing the same information in different contexts in different ways and creating questions based on it.

Generating questions using generative models: Neural networks trained on heuristic rules generated questions from the text.

Adaptive approach: Questions were complicated or simplified according to users' responses.

This method allows for the automatic question generation process to generate questions that are not only syntactically correct, but also include a logical and creative approach.

The working process of the automatic question generation method based on syntactic and heuristic approaches

Table 1.

No	Syntactic approach	Heuristic approach
1- Text analysis	Identifying key concepts and grammatical structures from the text (using NLP)	Semantic analysis of text and context detection
2- Template creation	Creating question templates based on predefined grammatical rules	Testing different options and creating flexible templates
3- Data placement	Incorporating words and phrases from the text into question templates	Generating different options of questions using generative models
4- Question optimization	Checking and correcting grammatical errors	Ensuring the semantic relevance and interest of the question
5- Adaptability	Determining the level of complexity of questions based on general rules	Adapting questions based on user responses
6-Final evaluation	Excluding incorrect or	Ensuring and optimizing the

and filtering

illogical questions

diversity of questions

The architecture of the automatic question generation method based on syntactic and heuristic approaches consists of the following main stages and components. This architecture is a combination of traditional Natural Language Processing (NLP) approaches based on strict rules and generative models, which ensures the generation of high-quality and flexible questions.

The architecture is divided into the following main parts:

Text reception and analysis:

1. Input

Text (Lecture, textbook, article, message, etc.)

User conversations (in Chat-bot or educational systems)

Data from previous questions

2. Text analysis and understanding

NLP tools (Tokenization, POS-tagging, Named Entity Recognition)

Syntactic analysis (Dependency parsing, Constituency parsing)

Semantic analysis (Word embeddings, Sentence embeddings)

Extraction of key information

3. Question generation module

Syntactic approach:

Predefined grammatical rules

Creation of question templates

Adaptation to the context of the text

Heuristic approach (Generative model-based question generation)

Transformer models

Paraphrasing and diversification of question types

Semantic compatibility checking

Question format development

Factual (Who? When? Where?)

Deep understanding (Why? How?)

Reasoning-based (What do you think?)

Fill-in-the-blank questions (Fill in the blank)

MCQ (Multiple Choice Questions)

4. Question evaluation and optimization

Grammar analysis (Grammarly, spaCy)

Logical checking (Ensure the question is clear and unambiguous)

Filtering ambiguous or incorrect questions

Eliminating duplicate questions

Assessing question complexity

5. Adaptive learning and improvement

Question quality analysis based on user responses
Adapting questions based on the level of difficulty of users
Reinforcement Learning for AI model self-improvement
Introducing new question templates and formats

6. Result

Questions (In various formats)
Tests with customized difficulty levels
Interactive Q&A using chatbot or AI
Learning systems (LMS, customized tests for e-learning)

The method of question generation based on syntactic and heuristic approaches has the advantages of grammatical correctness, flexibility, complex question generation, user-friendliness, speed, and efficiency. The combination of these approaches helps to further improve automatic question generation systems.

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